

Archipelago and Continent: Africanity in the Creole Indian Ocean

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The following is the transcript of a lecture given by Professor Ananya Jahanara Kabir in honour of Seychellois Africa activist, the late Achilles Kwame Luc. The lecture was organized by the Creole Language and Culture Research Institute at the University of Seychelles, and Bling Bling Poetry Association, to coincide with Africa Day on May 25, 2024. Ananya Jahanara Kabir is Professor of English Literature at Kings College, London.

Good afternoon! I am deeply honoured to deliver the annual Achille Kwame Luc Memorial Lecture on this joyous occasion of Fet’Afrik 2024.¹ Thank you to my colleagues for this gracious invitation. It is a precious opportunity to return to Seychelles and deepen our interpersonal and inter-institutional relations, and to continue researching this creole archipelago of the Western Indian Ocean from the perspective of an Indian person researching African, Creole, and Indian Ocean culture.² Seychelles is fascinating to me, because it seems connected to every part of the world I am interested in and feel connected to. But this deep sense of multiple connection is not the only reason I am invested in showcasing Seychelles to the wider world through my research. More crucially, the history, geography, and culture of Seychelles makes it a paradigm and test case for how creolized societies that crystallized within archipelagic settings may provide solutions to some of the most pressing issues facing our planet today. This is a conclusion I came to after an initial visit I made to Seychelles seven years ago.³

In November 2017, I undertook, together with my colleague Dr Elina Djebbari, a research trip to Seychelles, Mauritius, and Reunion Island. Our research objective in the Western Indian Ocean was to observe creolized dance forms in the present context as well as trace, through archival records, performance, and people’s memories, the histories of those dances. In that frame, we attended the annual Kreyol Festival celebrations in Seychelles. Focusing on dance-music complexes in these Indian Ocean archipelagos, our aim was to investigate their patronage, popularity and socio-cultural functions in the postcolonial era. We also wanted to ask: were these creolized music and dance histories of the Indian Ocean similar as well as different to those of the Atlantic world? We came away with far more than data corresponding to these precise questions. Our time in the Indian Ocean passed by in a blur of colour, music, movement, and tastes. We were struck by the warmth of people and their rich cultural heritage. Within this panorama, Seychelles emerged as full of potential.⁴

Three points struck me then about Seychelles: its deep commitment to a Creole identity, its geopolitical position as an archipelagic, African, Creole nation in the Indian Ocean,

and a keen interest in protecting its environment.⁵ Its desired autonomy regarding its resources is a valuable message for our precarious world. Like Mauritius, Seychelles is geopolitically African, on the crossroads between Asia and Africa, and influenced historically by Europe. Both nations have tried to combine Creole identity discourse with a high index of economic development and a balance between built infrastructure and the protection of natural heritage particularly within high-end tourism.⁶ Unlike Mauritius, however, where inter-ethnic politics overtakes narratives of creole harmony,⁷ Seychelles exhibits overtly a cohesive population which seems to have reconciled divergent interests through investing in Creole identity. In this era of global warming, neoliberalism, and right-wing politics, Seychelles appears to have achieved a balance. Despite the strength of alternative trends globally, and the pandemic's challenges, this balance – even if fragile – is being maintained.

What is it that Seychelles is doing right? It is urgent to investigate this question, for several reasons. Firstly, our answers can contribute to local attempts at self-valorisation – which, for a colonized and creolized society, is always work in progress. But we also need these answers to respond to a related set of questions: What forms does Africanity assume in the creolized, Afro-Asian space of the Indian Ocean world, and how do these archipelagic inflections impact commonly understood notions of Africanity as emanating from the 'mother continent'? The title of my lecture, 'Archipelago and Continent: Africanity in the Creole Indian Ocean', indicates my understanding of these issues as linked. Seychelles as a Creole Indian Ocean archipelago is not just a recipient of historical Africanity, but an active shaper of what Africa can and must mean on a planetary scale, today and tomorrow. For Achille Mbembe, Africa has the potential to initiate a different politics of inhabiting the Earth, of repairing and of sharing the planet.⁸ The archipelagic, creolized space of Seychelles can play a leading role in achieving this vision. To explain why, we can do no better than start with Mbembe's namesake – Achilles Kwame Luc himself – who embodied a Seychellois Africanity that swirled through the Creole Indian Ocean, reverberates on its shores and seeps through the hinterlands of the Asian and African continents.

Sak vakwa and African pendant: Fashioning a Seychellois Africanity

As this audience knows well, Achilles Kwame Luc was a multi-dimensional cultural activist. While mourning his untimely death on 29th October 2018, The Seychelles News Agency described him as 'a well-known artist, a promoter of the islands' rich culture and heritage, an environmentalist, an ardent supporter of human rights, and a peace lover'.⁹ For his friends, he made not just music but fresh juice; his passions included gardening and landscaping, protecting wildlife and biodiversity, and peace efforts – whether through the Peace Boat or the Daniel Pearl Days initiatives.¹⁰ These ostensibly diverse interests

cohere within a Creole worldview, wherein to protect the environment, care for one other, and draw sustenance from all resources at hand, constitute a toolkit for surviving and indeed thriving in adversity. Creolization involves inventive improvisation and creation of new culture through bricolage, the re-use of waste and fragments.¹¹ ‘What was special... was his way with kids, how he adapted and how spontaneous he was. I remember how after field trips he would collect seeds, which he assembled with other materials such as pet bottles. He would then get the kids to create music using these new instruments’, recalled Christelle Jacques.¹² Similar strategies were evident, too, in his self-fashioning. ‘A musician who was proud of his African roots, Kwame stood out – tall, in a locally made straw hat, red, yellow and green beads adorned to his dreadlocks. Around his neck were jewelries locally made from colourful beads, coconut shells and seashells. But one’s attention would be drawn to a big pendant in the shape of the African continent carved from wood. Completing his attire were a red, yellow and green shawl and a locally made bag from a fibre called ‘vakwa’ as Kwame was one of a handful of Seychellois still using the sak vakwa.’¹³

What is the meaning of that pendant alongside the sak vakwa? As the pendant’s shape signifies, embellishing oneself with a miniaturized version of the African continent is a clearly visible, clearly understood declaration of a personal and political affiliation to Africa. This externalization of Africanity is accompanied by another accessory of far more esoteric significance: a bag made from the fibre of *pandanus sechellarum* that is endemic to Seychelles.¹⁴ Its Creole name, ‘vakwa maron’, carries within it the history of enslavement and marronage: a relationship to the soil and its products that is unique to those who live and create culture on this archipelago alone.¹⁵ If wearing the pendant is a proclamation, even a defiant shout (I am African!! I belong to the mother continent!), carrying the bag is akin to a whisper: this is the secret of being Seychellois – the know-how of turning every fibre from the environment into utility and adornment – and it is ultimately the maroon’s secret too, that is absorbed by and diffused through a Creole society. Thus, a pendant that is an icon of the continent and a bag that is an index of the archipelago are worn together on the body of the cultural activist, to convey their contiguity, complementarity, and even, I would suggest, their interdependence. It is a relationship somewhat different from the invocation of archipelago and continent by St Lucian poet Derek Walcott in his Nobel Prize lecture of 1992 – in which he famously declared ‘Antillean art [as] this restoration of our shattered histories, our shards of vocabulary, our archipelago becoming a synonym for pieces broken off from the original continent’.¹⁶

Achilles Kwame Luc’s self-adornment communicates the embrace of another set of possibilities connecting archipelago and continent. To wear the pendant while carrying the sak vakwa is to perform a relationship that is less about being broken, broken off and drifting away, and more a living and active relationality arising from the ebb and flow of the Indian Ocean that connects continent and archipelago to generate an Afro-Asian Creole continuum. We know that, linking Walcott’s Caribbean archipelago and the

archipelagos of the Indian Ocean, such as Seychelles, is the economic institution of the plantation that triggered the settlement of these islands by peoples non-indigenous to them, and their consequent restructuring to serve the global capitalist machines generated by various European empires.¹⁷ But there are also key differences, which arise from the precolonial histories of the Indian Ocean world where Seychelles is located, and which enable Seychelles to participate in Africanity in a manner specific to the Indian Ocean world to which the eastern coastline of the continent, the big island of Madagascar, and several of the archipelagos of the Western Indian Ocean geopolitically belong.¹⁸ This play of divergences and similarities between those archipelagos and the islands and archipelagos of the Caribbean come together in Seychelles, to generate its potential within the project of repair on a planetary scale emanating outward from Africa that Achille Mbembe has envisaged as the way forward for our shared survival.

The Seychellois Creole garden: ‘gro manze’ as Indian Ocean resource

I now illustrate this potential of Seychelles, and the Africanity that runs through its history, geography, and culture, by turning to the Seychellois version of an institution characteristic of plantation economy across the Atlantic and Indian Ocean worlds – or should we call it a counterinstitution: the Creole garden. Following the Caribbean theorist Edouard Glissant’s theorization of the French Caribbean ‘jardin kreyol’, this phrase in its English translation has become a theoretical shorthand for the small plots of land which enslaved people cultivated to provide themselves with fruits, vegetables, and medicinal plants, ‘a small front or back garden arranged to permit the greatest possible biodiversity in the smallest possible space’.¹⁹ In offering the enslaved a sliver of space and time where their labour was focused on yields for their own nourishment and enjoyment, the Creole garden is contiguous to other creolized products of the plantation economy—including music, food, and language itself. All these cultural manifestations are part of the same paradox: they represent the maximal use of the minimal resources granted to the enslaved by the plantation system to keep them invested in life itself. In Sylvia Wynter’s words, ‘from early the planters gave the slaves plots of land on which to grow food to feed themselves in order to maximise profits’, which became ‘the focus of resistance to the market system and market values’ that the plantation represented and upheld; what Wynter calls ‘the inevitable and inbuilt confrontation between the plantation and the plot’ thus made the plot, and the Creole garden it supported, the ground of ‘cultural guerrilla resistance’, its ‘agricultural promiscuity’ constituting a ‘rich set of relations that contest domination’.²⁰

A legacy of the plantation economy, Creole gardens become its eventual antithesis: they promote crop diversity against monocropping, human subsistence over profit, and small-scale agricultural practices that support human health and the natural environment. They

thus uniquely articulate the relationship between the human and the natural environment enabled through local wisdom that survived through transoceanic diasporas, offer fertile grounds for researching the interconnection of cultural practices and solutions to the climate crisis, as well as researching the impact of globalization on sustainable heritage. That Creole gardens continue to offer resources for the present was demonstrated in detail by Dr Penda Choppy and her team in their report on ‘Creole Garden and Kitchen Pharmacy’, prepared for UNESCO: ‘During the COVID-19 lock-down period in Seychelles’, they observe, ‘our dependency on imported goods became glaringly clear as planes were suddenly reduced to carrying essential cargo... People started planting in pots if they lived in flats, and those who had land began planting typical Creole foodstuffs such as plantains, dessert bananas, yam, sweet potatoes, tomatoes and herbs. Many recipes and culinary achievements were shared over the social media. Most importantly, people shared recipes from the Creole garden and kitchen pharmacy for dealing with the COVID-19 symptoms and boosting the immune system’.²¹

Analysing the data collected from several interviews conducted for this investigation, Dr Choppy and her team concluded that ‘people began searching for their Creole identity as the COVID-19 pandemic had made them realize that through their Creole gardens, they could improve their food security and reduce the country’s carbon footprint’.²² This responsive-mode activation of an embodied archive of Creole knowledge is also an activation of the Africanity foundational to Creole lifeways as a reservoir of resources for survival in precarity imposed by the big machines of capitalism—from which are being generated the polycrises of our times, including climate change and the COVID-19 pandemic. Within the Creole garden, this Africanity manifests itself most evidently in the starchy foods that are the plantation economy’s fuel and life force. As Elizabeth DeLoughrey points out, ‘the provision grounds’ – which is what the Creole garden is called in Jamaica – ‘the provision grounds are understood as the often unseen – but no less integral – voluntary cultivation of subsistence foods such as yams, cassava, and sweet potatoes that represent edible staples and the economically viable roots of the internal markets’.²³ Different Creole languages signal this primacy through the names bestowed on this category – provisions or simply ‘food’ in the anglophone Caribbean – and ‘gro manze’ in Seychelles.²⁴ Using one category of provisions – the yam – also present in Seychelles, DeLoughrey elaborates on its theoretical importance for thinkers who have privileged it as ‘the primary roots culture of West Africa’.²⁵

For Sylvia Wynter, the yam is the foundation of a new social order even as for Kamau Braithwaite, it represents ‘a little piece of Africa on mourning ground’.²⁶ By examining Creole gardens in their writings, DeLoughrey presents the Africanity within the Creole gardens of diasporic populations as a balancing act between transplantation and (re)rooting. Yet as she also clarifies, ‘the yam is not, botanically speaking a root but rather a rhizome, suggesting a more lateral series of relationships’ through ‘a figurative model that is tied directly to Africa yet exceeds a singular root culture and emphasizes

regeneration in the wake of violence'.²⁷ This multiplicity makes the yam a tangible, edible, vegetal illustration of abstract theorizing around creolization as a rhizomatic structure, famously by Glissant himself.²⁸ As a rhizomatic network of value generated from existing resources, the Creole garden 'provided the space for folk knowledge, orality, resistance to commodification, and African and indigenous continuities'.²⁹ But the yam is already creolized: 'the tuber has both American and African origins' and it exemplifies how 'Creole gardens in the Caribbean were sites of intercropping of indigenous and African cultivars'.³⁰ The Creole garden is a living demonstration of not only how forced migration alters one's relationship to the land, but how it also necessitates relationships to other groups with their own relationship to the same land. Yam, cassava, and sweet potato all generate an Africanity constitutive of Creole experience and co-constitutive with cultures whose know-how is mobilized to make the garden productive for all.

Rozanmer, piman, bilimbi: Creolization as the Afro-Asian continuum

This re-reading of the Caribbean Creole garden through the yam can be incorporated into our analysis of Africanity in the creole Indian Ocean and particularly in Seychelles. There are a couple of issues to highlight in this regard. First, the 'intercropping between the indigenous and the African' which characterises the Caribbean Creole garden does not feature here, since – like the Mascarenes – the Seychelles archipelago was uninhabited before the European advent in the Indian Ocean world. Lacking indigenous savoir-faire on which the plantation settlers could draw, they had to bring to Seychelles all types of gro manze during the early phases of its settlement. 'As the national strategy for plant conservation makes clear', observes Dr Choppy and team, 'there are only a few native plants in Seychelles that are edible, so almost all our food plants have had to be introduced' – including the breadfruit which became the staple for the enslaved here.³¹ Secondly, these travelling plants enter the Seychelles Creole garden and the accompanying knowledge systems as categories supplementary to the gro manze, but key to the completeness and efficacy of the Creole garden. Epistemologically, the Seychellois Creole garden corresponds to the Kanmtole as a hold-all filing system.³² Those whom Dr Choppy's team interviewed for their UNESCO project agreed that: 'The creole garden must contain a specific category of plants to be considered as such. These are: starchy foods ('gro manze'); condiments; vegetables; fruits; herbs and medicinal plants; animals; flowers.'³³ Of these the most abundant plants are the rozanmer or Madagascar periwinkle, the piman or chilli pepper, the papaya, and the sour fruit called bilimbi.

Where have these now-assimilated vegetal elements within Seychellois creole culture come from? The names – whether scientific or popular – point to an assemblage of provenances ranging from Madagascar, to which the periwinkle is endemic – to the bilimbi, which is native to Maluku Islands of Indonesia. While the bilimbi, carambola,

and jamblon were spread through the Indian Ocean world by the Portuguese and Dutch, the papaya, like the chilli pepper, was domesticated in Mesoamerica before being introduced to Europe, Asia and Africa by Iberian colonizers.³⁴ Hence, the routes through which these constituents of the Seychellois Creole garden have travelled present no straight line between origin and destination but are the result of transcultural botanic exchanges across the entire East-West spread of the Indian Ocean. Within this networked space, points on the African continent are essential nodes. Before the Europeans entered this space, the catalysts for transculturation were Arab traders and, before them, it was the Austronesian seafarers who carried with them the cultures and nautical technologies of the Pacific Ocean to shape the Indian Ocean world; the European colonizers were themselves often vectors for subaltern botanical knowledges being carried by the enslaved from African mainland eastwards across the Indian Ocean world as far as Dejima in Japan. And indeed, as with the coconut palm, no human carrier seems to have been needed; the waves of the ocean and the monsoon winds played the role of vector.³⁵

The question then is – is creolization in Seychelles creating an Africanity that is broken (off) from the continent of Africa, or is this an instance of Africanity that is swirled through these human and non-human vectors through Afro-Asian space to assume its own epistemic and ontological validity? Writers from East Africa such as Abdul Razak Gurnah and Yvonne Adhiambo Owuor have been showing us through their novels that to be connected across the Afro-Asian space is not an aberration: rather it is an intrinsic part of being African. The preferred location of Gurnah's and Owuor's narratives are the archipelagos and islands off the coast of East Africa's nations – Zanzibar and Lamu. There are two ways in which these archipelagos differ from Seychelles: they are very close to the coastline, and they are part of two continental nations, Tanzania and Kenya respectively. These reasons also mean that they lack full representational autonomy from the continental landmass – even though it can be argued that the novelists use fiction to try and free them from that tie. This pressure is evident in even Owuor's terminology for the Indian Ocean, 'the Swahili Seas', which draws us back to the coastline where the Swahili speakers are spread. In contrast, as an independent nation situated far from any continental coastline, promoting Creole culture and language as national heritage, it is Seychelles that can bring best the benefits of an archipelagic and creolized approach to rethinking Africanity.

This is an approach that admittedly does not come to mind immediately when considering what or where 'Africa' may be. For instance, at a recent conference on the arts of the Indian Ocean held in Toronto, a scholar lamented that, as an 'Africanist', he wished there had been more representation of Africa at the conference. Yet the very first panel was dedicated to the circulation of *coco de mer* objects in the Indian Ocean world and thus to Seychelles. Evidently for many Africanists, Seychelles is not at the forefront of thinking what 'Africa in the Indian Ocean' might mean. But I found the prominence given to Seychelles through the opening panel a promising embrace of the potential of archipelagic

thinking in the African context. In recent years, a body of thought has developed around archipelagos as a model for positing connections between dispersed and fragmented entities and using these connections to understand the solidarities that can emerge out of them.³⁶ Archipelagic thinking contributes to the wider work around reparation and decoloniality by emphasizing the equal worth of the small and dispersed island fragment and the large, apparently unbroken, continent, even while underlining the material differences between archipelagic and continental forms of identity assertion and perception: in the words of Wendy Knepper, ‘it is possible that the seams and scars of the Caribbean bricolage reflect in part the differences between the African-American constitution of identity as rooted in black experience and the Caribbean construct of identity as a plurality, reflected in the intermixture of cultures or the geographic image of the archipelago’.³⁷

Creole garden as epistemology: Planetary Africa’s archipelagic linkages

The conjuncture of archipelagic geography and cultural plurality, seen in Seychelles as well as the Caribbean, is not simply a static marker of their divergence from the continents they are linked to historically, economically, and geologically: it is also an activator of what Jeannine Murray-Ronan calls ‘Creole care webs’ that the Creole garden exemplifies. As she concludes, ‘the Jardin Créole and the multiple types of relations – between people, between people and plants, across generations function as a structure for caring more, for defining care ever more expansively and experimentally, and for locating such expansive definitions in the historical legacies of Atlantic slavery’.³⁸ Seychelles carries these definitions over beyond the Cape of Good Hope and link those legacies to the Indian Ocean world. Another Africa becomes visible – one where the continent itself is creolized through the archipelagic networks it is suspended in. Africa’s archipelagos and islands link creolization as a cultural process from the Atlantic coast – Cape Verde and Liberia – to the Western Cape and East Africa – the Creole cultures of Seychelles, and the Mascarenes as well as the Swahili seas. Despite diverse investigations into creolized cultures on the African continent, some the product of the European encounter, others generated within other regional complexes, they are confined to disciplinary or geographic silos.

Can Seychelles become a Creole garden where different strands of research and activism around creolization across the African continent, can be brought together to re-creolize Africa from the Indian Ocean? This ‘garden’ can bring together creolization of enclaves alongside with creolization of islands, assess mercantile and plantation economies as twin motors of the processes of cultural innovation under duress that we understand as creolization. New ways to (de)centre Africa and Africanity can bypass or counter nativist assertions while opening up unexpected approaches to considerations of racial justice as well as interdisciplinarity, that move away from terrestrial conceptualization of history

and identity and privilege instead the view from archipelagos. The creolized embodiment of identity, culture, heritage, and responsibility towards the planet that offers pathways of belonging and action alternative to those dictated by territorial constraints is susceptible to the pressures of globalization and territoriality. The Institute for Creole Language and Culture and activists such as Achille Kwame Luc have been activating this heritage for future Seychellois people as bearers of a non-continental version of Africanity in relation and dialogue with all the cultures that wash up on the many islands of this archipelago. Maryse Condé once asked: 'Cannot the Creole culture be transplanted and survive just as well through the use of memory? Aren't there new and multiple versions of créolité?'³⁹ We can also ask: can there be then older and pre-existing versions of 'being Creole'? Creolization is not just the horizon of the present, it is the future of the past. Seychelles presents not just another version of what 'Africa' is, but another vision of what 'Africa' can and must be for the future.

¹<http://www.seychellesnewsagency.com/articles/20634/%22Africanity+in+the+Creole+Indian+Ocean+%22+lecture+held+in+honour+of+Seychellois+artist>

²Ananya Jahanara Kabir, 'Creole Bengal, or What Are We? A Personal Journey through Words and Worlds'. *Fondas Kréyol*. <https://www.fondaskreyol.org/article/creole-bengal-or-what-are-we-a-personal-journey-through-words-and-worlds>

³ This field trip was part of a month-long journey through Mauritius, Reunion, and Seychelles, timed to coincide with the Creole Day festivities throughout the Western Indian Ocean archipelagos. It was conducted within 'Modern Moves', an ERC Advanced Grant-funded research project on the global popularity of African-heritage dance directed by me, that ran from 2013 to 2018 and is archived at www.modernmoves.org.uk. For the final report, see <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/324198/reporting/it>

⁴ We did some justice to this potential through two publications: see Ananya Jahanara Kabir, 'Creolization as balancing act in the transoceanic quadrille: Choreogenesis, incorporation, memory, market'. *Atlantic Studies: Global Currents*, 17.1 (2020), pp.135-157; and Elina Djebbari, 'Mémoire, musique et créolisation aux Seychelles'. *Esclavages & Post-esclavages. Slaveries & Post-Slaveries* 7 (2022, n.p.). At <http://journals.openedition.org/slaveries/7902>; DOI : <https://doi.org/10.4000/slaveries.7902>

⁵ See the late Thomas Hylland Eriksen's approach to Seychelles within his larger concerns around the world's 'overheating', especially Thomas Hylland Eriksen, 'Between Inequality and Difference: the Creole World in the Twenty-First Century'. *Global Networks*, 19.1 (2019), pp.3-20; Thomas Hylland Eriksen, 'Creolisation as a Recipe for Conviviality', in *Conviviality at the Crossroads: The Poetics and Politics of Everyday Encounters*, ed. Oscar Hemer, Maja Povrzanović Frykman, and Per-Markku Ristilampi (Springer Nature, 2020), pp.43-63.

⁶ Ali Zafar, 'Mauritius: An Economic Success Story', in *Yes Africa Can: Success Stories from a Dynamic Continent*, ed. Punam Chuhan-Pole and Manka Angwafo (The World Bank, 2011), pp.91-106; Liam Campling and Rosalie Michel (2006). 'Sustaining Social Development in a Small Island Developing State? The Case of Seychelles'. *Sustainable Development*, 14 (2), pp.115-125.

⁷ Rosa M. Beunel (2019). 'Islands within an Island: the Reluctant Creolisation of Franco-Mauritians and Little-Whites in Dormann and Agénor's novels'. *Carnets de recherches de l'océan Indien*, 4, pp.83-95; Rosa M.C. Beunel-Fogarty (2024). 'Natasha Soobramanien's Aesthetic of Archipelagic Memory: A Literary Methodology of Political Solidarity'. *Monsoon*, 2 (1), pp.58-67; Rosa M.C. Beunel-Fogarty (2024). 'Creolization and Gender: Island Imaginings in Ananda Devi's *Pagli* and Its Sequel'. *Verge: Studies in Global Asias*, 10 (2), pp.138-160.

⁸ Achille Mbembe, *Out of the Dark Night: Essays on Decolonization* (Columbia University Press, 2021); see also Achille Mbembe, *Critique of Black Reason*, Trans. Laurent Dubois (NC: Duke University Press, 2016), pp.178-183.

⁹ Sharon Ernesta, 'Rainbow Nation of Seychelles Loses One of its Most Colourful Sons'. *Seychelles News Agency*, 29 October 2018. Accessible at:

<http://www.seychellesnewsagency.com/articles/9975/Rainbow+nation+of+Seychelles+loses+one+of+its+most+colourful+sons>

¹⁰ Ernesta, 'Rainbow Nation'.

¹¹ Nigel O. Bolland (1998). 'Creolisation and Creole Societies: a Cultural Nationalist View of Caribbean Social History'. *Caribbean Quarterly*, 44 (1-2), pp.1-32; see also Ananya Jahanara Kabir (2023). 'The Creolizing Turn and its Archipelagic Directions'. *Cambridge Journal of Postcolonial Literary Inquiry*, 10 (1), pp.90-103.

¹² Cited in Ernesta, 'Rainbow Nation.'

¹³ Ernesta, 'Rainbow Nation'.

¹⁴ Michael B. Usher (1993). 'The Vallée de Mai, Praslin, Seychelles'. *Environmental Conservation* 20 (4), pp.356-358.

¹⁵ On the maroon and marronage, see Edouard Glissant, *Poetics of Relation*, Trans. Betsy Wing (University of Michigan Press, 1997), pp.71-2, and Stéphanie Melyon-Reinette, ed., *Marronage and Arts: Revolts in Bodies and Voices* (Cambridge Scholars Publishing, 2012); Ronald Cummings (2010). '(Trans) Nationalisms, Marronage, and Queer Caribbean Subjectivities'. *Transforming Anthropology* 18 (2), pp.169-180.

¹⁶ Derek Walcott, 'The Antilles: Fragments of Epic Memory,' Nobel Prize Lecture (December 7, 1992), in *Nobel Lectures in Literature 1991–1995*, ed. Sture Allén (World Scientific Publishing, 1997), cited from <http://www.nobel.se/literature/laureates/1992/walcott-lecture.html>

¹⁷ Antonio Benítez-Rojo, *The Repeating Island: The Caribbean and the Postmodern Perspective* (Duke University Press, 1997); Françoise Vergès, 'Indian-Oceanic creolizations: Processes and Practices of Creolization on Réunion Island', in *Creolization: History, Ethnography, Theory*, ed. Charles Stewart (Routledge, 2007), pp.133-152.

¹⁸ For some of these differences, see Françoise Lionnet (2011). 'Cosmopolitan or Creole Lives? Globalized Oceans and Insular Identities'. *Profession*, pp.23-43, and Françoise Vergès and Carpanin Marimoutou (2012). 'Moorings: Indian ocean Creolisations', *PORTAL: Journal of Multidisciplinary International Studies* 9 (1), pp.1-39.

¹⁹ Jeanine Murray-Román (2022). 'Care Webs and the Creole Garden in Manthia Diawara's *Édouard Glissant: One World in Relation*'. *French Screen Studies* 22 (1), pp.77-90, 77; for Glissant's views, see *ibid.*, 87, n. 8.

²⁰ Sylvia Wynter (1971). 'Novel and History, Plot and Plantation'. *Savacou* 5, pp.95–102, at 99, 102, 100; Murray-Román, 'Care Webs', p.84 and p.82.

²¹ Penda Choppy, 'Seychelles: The Creole Garden and Kitchen Pharmacy', *UNESCO Intangible Heritage Case Studies: Supporting Research and Documentation of Indigenous Knowledge Systems on Biodiversity Conservation, Climate Change and Disaster Risk Reduction in Eastern Africa* (UNESCO Regional Office for Eastern Africa, 2021), pp.65-86.

²² Choppy, 'The Creole Garden', p.67.

²³ Elizabeth Deloughrey (2011). 'Yam, Roots, and Rot: Allegories of the Provision Ground'. *Small Axe* 15 (1), pp. 58-75.

²⁴ Choppy, 'The Creole Garden', p.76.

²⁵ Deloughrey, 'Yam, Roots, and Rot'.

²⁶ Wynter, 'Novel and History'; Edward Kamau Brathwaite, 'Afternoon of the Status Crow', lecture at the University of Bremen, June 1980; Savacou Working Paper 1, 1982, 14b, cited by Deloughrey, 'Yam, Roots, and Rot', p.61, n.16.

²⁷ DeLoughrey, 'Yams, Roots, and Rot', pp.61- 62.

²⁸ Neal A. Allar (2019). 'Rhizomatic Influence: the Antigenealogy of Glissant and Deleuze', *Cambridge Journal of Postcolonial Literary Inquiry* 6 (1), pp.1-13.

²⁹ DeLoughrey, 'Yams, Roots, and Rot', p.64.

³⁰ DeLoughrey, 'Yams, Roots, and Rot', p.61, p.58.

³¹ Choppy, 'The Creole Garden', p.70.

³² See Kabir, 'Creolization as Balancing Act', pp.148-50.

³³ Choppy, 'The Creole Garden', p.76.

³⁴ Rene B. Javellana (2015). 'Global Exchange: Glimpses of an 18th-Century Colonial Kitchen in Manila'. *Kritika Kultura* 24, pp.3-88

³⁵ A. N. Damania (2013). 'The Coco-de-mer or the Double Coconut (*Lodoicea maldivica*): Myths and Facts'. *Journal of Asian Agri-History* 17 (4), pp.299-309.

³⁶ See Ananya Jahanara Kabir and Luca Raimondi (2024). 'Archipelagic Memory and Indian Ocean Literary Studies: An Introduction'. *Monsoon* 2.(1),pp.3-12; Kabir, 'Creolization and the Archipelagic Turn'.

³⁷ Wendy Knepper (2007). 'Colonization, Creolization, and Globalization: The Art and Ruses of Bricolage'. *Small Axe* 10 (3), pp.70-86.

³⁸ Murray-Román, 'Creole Care Webs', p.77.

³⁹ Maryse Condé, "Créolité without Creole Language?," in *Caribbean Creolization: Reflections on the Cultural Dynamics of Language, Literature and Identity*, ed. Kathleen M. Balutansky and Marie-Agnès Sourieau (University Press of Florida, 1998), pp.106–07 and p.109.